

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers,

Welcome to the 6th regular issue in 2017 with three high quality regular papers and two papers from the focused topic “*Recommender systems and social network analysis*”.

As always, I'd like to thank all reviewers for their support and efforts during the evaluation process of the articles. Furthermore, I'd particularly like to acknowledge the generous support of the members of the J.UCS consortium which enables us to continue to offer J.UCS as an open content journal without publication fees.

In regular issue, I am very glad to introduce three accepted high quality papers from authors from three different countries.

Mario Bravetti from Italy and France proposes in his paper a middleware based on client-server protocols and on a set primitives, for managing resources and executing programs in Web Operating Systems, which is based on an extension of the REST architecture. Julia Kasch, Peter van Rosmalen and Marco Kalz from The Netherlands discuss their work on a framework supporting educational scalability, in particular assessment and feedback, applied for Open Online Courses. Andre Rodrigues Oliveira, Ulisses Dias and Zanoni Dias from Brazil report their research about a polynomial-time approximation algorithm for the Sorting by Reversals and Transpositions Problem.

In their guest editorial, the editors of the focused topic, Alexander Felfernig from Graz University of Technology, Austria, Ralf Klamma from RWTH Aachen, Germany, Tobias Ley from Tallinn University, Estonia, and Dominik Kowald, Elisabeth Lex and Viktoria Pammer-Schindler from Graz University of Technology & Know-Center, Austria, write:

“The papers in this focused topic are invited extensions of papers presented at the Workshop on Recommender Systems and Big Data Analytics (RS-BDA 2016), co-located with the i-Know 2017, the International Conference on Knowledge Technologies and Data-driven Business. The i-Know conference series aims at advancing research at the intersection of disciplines such as Knowledge Discovery, Semantics, Information Visualization, Visual Analytics, Social (Semantic) and Ubiquitous Computing. The goal of integrating these approaches is to augment human intelligence by designing tools and services, which interact naturally with humans, learn from their experiences and generate and evaluate evidence-based hypotheses.

The articles specifically deal with research from the fields of recommender systems and social network analysis. Specifically, the paper written by Mohsen Shahriari, Sabrina Haefele and Ralf Klamma from RWTH Aachen in Germany addresses the use of recommendations to identify overlapping communities in Online

collaboration systems. By using term frequency of words generated by users and combining them with an extended clustering technique, the authors propose an algorithm, which could be useful in question & answer forums to suggest missing links between users. The second article written by Rebekka Alm from Fraunhofer IGD Rockstock in Germany, however, demonstrates the use of recommendations to foster information exchange in production. The author proposes a framework that uses annotations in combination with a formalized knowledge base to represent working domains and illustrate the usefulness of this approach via the example of an assembly assistance system.”

Enjoy Reading!

Cordially,

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